

Project Planning for The Development of an E-Learning Interactive Educational Platform in Industrial Engineering-Based Applications

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Abstract

Current socio-economic developments generated by the SARS-Cov2 outbreak have pushed e-learning into the spotlight more than ever before. With imminent high-performance expectations from e-learning management systems the academic society has found itself in an unprecedented situation, struggling to adapt to the swift change from face-to-face activities to online teaching. A thorough state of the art analysis on e-learning solutions led to the identification of several gaps, like: a lack in statistical control for confounding factors when calculating improvement in learning; available blended learning solutions are scarce in the industrial or mechanical engineering areas; customization of content is difficult at an individual level, particularly for large theoretical classes. To overcome these gaps, authors propose a detailed management planning procedure for the design and development of an e-learning interactive educational platform able to generate and deliver a student-centered customized curriculum for complex project development in industrial engineering-based applications. The e-learning solution aims to integrate a Curriculum Route Builder, which could allow the identification and interpretation of real individual needs of one learner and integrate them into the general goal of the designed subject curriculum. To help achieve the main objective of the research, twelve specific objectives have been defined. A comprehensive workplan was developed, made up of four work packages. Each work package has associated specific activities, estimated results, key success indicators and deliverables. Risk analysis was undertaken and with a 1.82 score it was concluded that the risk incidence rate is low. After allocation of resources, it was established that three laboratories are needed to implement the project, all within a total budget of 449996.0 lei.

Keywords: Hybrid Education, Custom Curriculum, Learning Objectives, Project Planning.

Introduction

Marope M. et al. (2017) conclude that from a socio-economic and cultural point of view, curricula must enable learners to acquire competences which allow them to properly address the requirements of a demanding labor

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market, all in a complex and fast changing environment due to Industry 4.0 and Artificial Intelligence influences. According to Harward D. (2017) audience is hyper connected to personal devices and usually expects at least the same level of engagement and excitement from any form of teaching/ learning/ training activity to show interest. Several approaches have been shown to shift the learning experience from teacher-centered instruction toward innovative, student-centered teaching, like: project-based learning as stated by Jensen A.A. et al. (2019) in their work; team-based approaches, as discussed by Mal P.R., Suneel P. (2019); blended learning, as presented by several researchers like First A.I. and Ayse A. (2019), Sahni J. (2019) or Dias S.B. and Diniz J.A. (2014); and even gamification of content, as presented by Subhash S. and Cudney E.A. (2018) and Alomari I. et al. (2019). These are rapidly becoming mainstream, as Dziuban C. et al. (2018) identifies that the labor market requires more and more competences like creativity, critical thinking, complex problem solving, deductive reasoning and social intelligence. OECD (2018) forecasts that, in the future, graduates will have to apply their knowledge in unknown and evolving circumstances, needing a broad range of skills, including cognitive and meta-cognitive skills (e.g. critical thinking, creative thinking, learning to learn and self-regulation); social and emotional skills (e.g. empathy, self-efficacy and collaboration); and practical and physical skills (e.g. using new information and communication technology devices). Garrison D.R. and Kanuka H. (2004) state that more and more commonly used, hybrid or blended learning refers to a combination of face-to-face learning, including but not confined to lectures, and online learning.

From a scientific point of view, Twigg C.A. (2003) classifies blended/ hybrid learning courses in four main categories: replacement, supplemental, emporium or buffet, depending on the relationship between the face-to-face and online components of the curricula. The replacement model involves that face-to-face lectures are substituted either partially or fully by online material, and class meeting time is either reduced or repurposed. Bowen W.G. (2012) shows that the most common practice is to require students to watch videos online prior to coming to class and/or to complete some type of assignment. Repurposing of lecture time can mean: • Answer students' questions; • Provide traditional recitation sessions or optional remedial sessions; • Give students the opportunity—or require them—to participate in discussions or active learning exercises. The supplemental model analyzed by Twigg C.A. (2003) assumes that students to attend the same number of class meetings, but to access technology-based materials outside of the classroom as additional resources. In the emporium model, students work solely online but within a "learning resource center". The buffet model, as, for example, implemented by Ohio State University and recorded by Pearl D. (2003), provides students with a menu of learning activities in both face-to-face and online formats, being the most flexible of the blended learning opportunities.

As implementation of blended learning solutions within higher education institutions is becoming a more common practice, at an international level, feedback on its' impact varies across specialists like Lack K.A. (2013) noted. One major drawback identified by Zhao Y. and Breslow L. (2013) is that most studies lack a statistical control for confounding factors when calculating improvement in learning.

One of the most important limitation of the existing blended learning solutions, is that they are currently delivered with a pre-planned curriculum workflow structure. In order to be truly customizable, a curriculum should allow each learner to have an individual learning experience, while achieving the same learning objectives across the same subject.

Another significant drawback of current blended curriculum design is being less concerned with individual learning styles, leaving students confused with the amount of available information. One major downside of this approach is that students who are not responsive to this model tend to fall behind, because of decreased levels of engagement and motivation. Available blended learning curricula offer solutions only for lecture or seminar-based subjects, leaving a gap for laboratory intensive subjects, like engineering classes, where specific equipment and materials are required for the teaching experience to be effective. Out of the 42 studies reviewed by Zhao Y. and Breslow L. (2013) not one was industrial or mechanical engineering based.

Considering the abovementioned, the authors propose a detailed management planning procedure for the design and development of an e-learning interactive educational platform (HYBRID-ED) able to generate and deliver a student-centered customized curriculum for complex project development in industrial engineering-based applications. The HYBRID-ED initiative is approached as a project which tackles the above-mentioned disadvantages of current approaches, by providing a fully customizable curricula for complex project development in engineering-based applications, within an e-learning educational platform.

The challenges of the proposed approach will be to design a fully customizable Curriculum Route Builder (CRB), which will allow to identify and interpret the real individual needs of one learner and integrate them into the general goal of the designed subject curriculum. The CRB is developed using the following programming environment: LabView toolkits, CSS and PHP modules.

The importance of the proposed hybrid learning solution resides in its' applicability for a continuously evolving and more demanding target audience. Once implemented the hybrid education e-learning platform will be a cost efficient and convenient solution for higher education institutions. It will offer options for monitoring, assessing and evaluation of the following main parameters: learner progress; trainer performance; consumable material stocks; equipment performance and maintenance status. Computer aided project planning software solutions (like Primavera P6) will be used to design custom resource workflows. The project is proposed to be implemented at POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest (UPB) from Romania.

Hereafter, the main management planning tools are presented in detail for the successful implementation of the HYBRID-ED initiative.

Study background and methods

Since the Future Shock's inception written by the futurist Toffler A. (1970), in connection with the educational system, a question which does not yet have an appropriate answer, has arisen: „Why is everything massified in the system, rather than individualized in the system?“. The concept of "customized learning" becomes more and more current, as, according to Toffler, „new technologies make possible customization in a way that the old system — everybody reading the same textbook at the same time — did not offer“. His ideas are now made possible through the buffet model proposed by the current research, according to Twigg's C.A. (2003) classification. The new approach is that of considering each learner different and customizing the teaching activities and the contents specifically for that individual, in an „education mass customization system“ able to both reduce customizations costs and offer targeted teaching for each different person. A lot of e-learning platforms are available, but they are working in the same way, letting teachers to upload courses (the same for all learners) and learners to access them. HYBRID-ED offers the solution for staying in the middle of the subject with an innovative technology-breaking suggestion: hybrid learning, containing a set of characteristics able to be offered in an education mass customization system: customized, on-line contents of courses, teaching-on-demand, multimedia and interactive teaching materials, in a word, a powerful IT platform, based on artificial intelligence algorithms, able to conceive and offer a „menu“ of learning activities in both face-to-face and on-line formats. This type of teaching must be provided in special classrooms, having a state-of-the-art endowment in terms of gadgets, computers and communication facilities. This is the image of the future education, and HYBRID-ED has the resource to fulfil this image and to concretize it.

The impact in the socio-economic and cultural environment is given by the broad range of skills the system can provide, including cognitive and meta-cognitive skills; social and emotional skills; and practical and physical skills. The platform runs artificial intelligence meta-algorithms able to identify the need of the learner for a certain type of skills, according to a set of initial tests and to customize the scientific content of the courses, by combining different modules and to generate new content, learner dependent. Thus, the project could change the way the students and the faculty see and understand the teaching and learning process, in the 21st century, by offering to each learner what he/she needs for personal evolution.

The impact in scientific environment is given by the new technology the platform uses and by the novelty of the algorithms and of the working mode. This could boost the universities on the road of introducing new technologies in the teaching process. The integrated platform could open new doors in the higher educational system, by exploring new applicative directions in the field of new education methods in the Industry 4.0 era. It is an opportunity for high schools and universities to discover an open teaching-learning system connected with the nowadays technology evolution.

The current e-learning solution used at UPB is a static Moodle platform. HYBRID-ED is aimed to be integrated within the learning opportunities of the Faculty of Industrial Engineering and Robotics from UPB, thus improving efficiency, learner and trainer compliance, whilst addressing the globalized issue of education transformation.

The development of a fully functional industrial engineering product is considered, in the context of the current initiative, a complex project design task (Figure 1). There are three main systems of any industrial engineering complex project, namely: mechanical system, software system, electronical system.

Figure 1: Life cycle of project implementation – methods and instruments of investigation

The projects' main objective is to design and develop an e-learning interactive educational platform able to generate and deliver a student-centered customized curriculum for complex project development in industrial engineering-based applications. The e-platform must assess the initial state of the students, from educational requirements point of view and to generate and adapt a customized curriculum for each person, being the first generative e-learning platform in the field of industrial engineering. The innovation level, novelty and originality of the implementation is derived from the way the curriculum is customized, in a generative approach controlled by artificial intelligence meta-algorithms, by selecting available knowledge in three different fields, mechanic, electronic and software, on three different levels (beginner, intermediate and advanced) and many different types of delivering the knowledge, based on the initial level of competencies of the students, identified also automatically. Calculating improvement in learning, has been shown by previous research conducted by Zhao Y., Breslow L. (2013), to lack in statistical control for confounding factors. The currently proposed initiative integrates validated scientific instruments, methods and methodologies for quantitative and qualitative measurement of learning improvement of subjects.

To support the main objective and further demonstrate the elements originality, twelve specific objectives have been defined, as follows: SO1. Identify the educational needs for industrial engineering based higher education learners; SO2. Define accurate cognitive learning objectives, behavioral learning objectives and learning outcomes in correlation with complex project design systems: mechanical, software, electrical; SO3. Develop a Curriculum Builder software tool, that evaluates and interprets real individual needs of learners. Algorithms are be defined for automatically generating a custom route curriculum for student centered learning; SO4. Develop a Task Book (TB) for a hybrid e-learning platform. The TB contains product, process and system requirements and specifications (RS), identifying in a precise and measurable way what the hybrid e-learning platform must do and how it must perform in order to satisfy the customer needs; SO5. Design the hybrid e-learning interactive educational platform architecture and functionalities; SO6. Program and implement the generative algorithms into the hybrid platform; SO7. Develop curriculum modules for complex project design in industrial engineering applications; SO8. Design and test a Pilot course for hybrid e-learning; Pilot testing also involves the undertaking of statistical analysis for result significance and validation; SO9. Test and improve design of the hybrid e-learning interactive educational platform; SO10. Develop the customized curriculum for each learner; SO11. Design an experimental plan with multivariable regression analysis using DOE. This provides a scientifically valid instrument for the development and interpretation of Surface maps for individual learner evolution; SO12. Disseminate results through scientific research publications in ISI journal and conference proceedings.

A sustainable and realistic objective of the project is to integrate the final version of the hybrid e-learning platform within the learning opportunities of the Faculty of Industrial Engineering and Robotics from UPB.

Project Planning

The Curriculum Route Builder (CRB) is the first initiative of its' kind, which could allow the identification and interpretation of real individual needs of one learner and integrate them into the general goal of the designed subject curriculum. The CRB programming considers an extended set of the following seven initial input parameters:

learning style, instructional strategy, delivery method, assessment method, competency (knowledge, skills, abilities) level, complexity level and personal preferences. The extended set is obtained through needs analysis.

Hybrid curriculum efficiency progress evaluation implies the usage of both quantitative and qualitative assessment methods, showing both what students learned and, also, how they can apply, synthesize, evaluate, and design what they have learned. Significance of the obtained results are established using an independent t-test using SPSS software. Final evaluation of the hybrid curriculum is done with design of experiments (DOE) implemented through Design-Expert V11 Software for multivariable regression analysis. Dependent and independent variables are based on the defined cognitive and behavioral learning objectives of the hybrid curriculum.

The development and implementation of such a bold initiative requires a thorough project planning. Hereafter, the project workplan (Table 1) and main activities are described in detail.

Table 1: Project Work Plan: Work packages, activities and achievement of corresponding specific objectives (%)

Work packages and activities	2020							2021							2022								
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23
WP1. Curriculum requirements and specifications	WP1																						
A1.1. Needs analysis for engineering based higher education learners	A1.1							SO1 (100%), SO2 (100%)															
A1.2. Design of custom route curriculum builder (RCB) for student centred learning		A1.2						SO3 (100%)															
A1.3. Establishing the requirements and specifications for the functional platform architecture			A1.3					SO4 (100%)															
WP2. Architecture and detailed design of hybrid e-learning platform								WP2															
A2.1. Architecture design of Alfa version for hybrid e-learning platform								A2.1							SO5(70%), SO6(50%)								
A2.2. Design of content curriculum modules for complex project design in engineering applications								A2.2					SO7 (80%)										
A2.3. Pilot course development and testing for complex project design								A2.3					SO6(40%), SO7(20%), SO8 (100%)										
A2.4. Interpretation of results and improvement of architecture design													A2.4										
WP3. Implementation and method demonstration															WP3								
A3.1. Design and implementation of Beta version for hybrid e-learning platform								SO5 (30%), SO6 (10%), SO9 (80%), SO10 (100%)							A3.1								
A3.2. Repeatability tests and validation of final hybrid e-learning platform								SO9 (20%), SO11 (100%)							A3.2								
WP4. Project management and result dissemination								WP4 SO12 (100%)															
A4.1. Project management								A4.1															
A4.2. Publication writing for conferences and journals								A4.2															
A4.3. Conference participations and study visits				A4.3				A4.3						A4.3						A4.3			

WP1: Curriculum requirements and specifications

The first Work Package (WP1) is comprised of three main activities (A1.1 – A1.3) and is planned to be implemented during a period of seven months (M1 – M7). Hereafter, the detailed activities, estimated results, key success indicators and deliverables are described in detail.

A1.1.(M1-M3): A needs analysis is undertaken for three main systems of a complex industrial engineering project: mechanical system, software system, electrical system. The main assessment tools are: questionnaires, interviews and focus groups. The target group of the project is 1200 undergraduate students, representing all undergraduate students, from year 1 to 4, studying in the industrial engineering domain, enrolled at UPB. The sample group for the

needs analysis is comprised of 100 students, selected randomly out of the 1200, to preserve statistical significance of the study. All materials for questionnaires, interviews and focus group are designed in accordance with the graduates' necessary competence set, which is defined by RNCIS in the diploma supplements of graduates from industrial engineering domain. The question/ item structure follows both Ulrich K. and Eppinger's S. (2015) methodology. The needs analysis considers the evaluation of 7 initial CRB input parameters. The need reports includes, for all three systems of a complex industrial engineering project, the following mandatory elements: an extended set of CRB input parameters, sets of cognitive and behavioral learning objectives, set of learning outcomes, for each domain. Learning objectives are defined using Bloom's revised taxonomy as described by Gershon M. (2018). Complexity Levels as defined by Schaffernicht M.F.G. and Groesser S.N. (2016) are also be taken into account, in the needs analysis. (LAB 1)/ A1.2. (M2-M7): Using the extended set of the input parameters, learning objectives and learning outcomes, the team members construct a CRB process design flow chart using Lucidchart software. This step allows a perspective view of the generative solution needed for CRB design and implementation, allowing data to be paired with insight, at each individual step of the flowchart. CRB involves a generative programming approach, controlled by artificial intelligence meta-algorithms. LabView, C++ and Microsoft's Intentional Programming software are used to design the CRB in accordance with the constructed flowchart. The final CRB is embedded in the in the architecture of the hybrid e-learning platform. (LAB 2)/ A1.3. (M2-M7): Requirements and specifications (RS) are defined in order to identify in a precise and measurable way what the hybrid e-learning platform must do and how it has to perform in order to satisfy the customer needs. Three categories are considered for the analysis, namely: product, process and system requirements and specifications. In order to quantify the RS a list of metrics is put together, assigning them relative importance, limit and ideal values. The instructional tools used in RS identification and construction are described in the previous work of authors Doicin C. and Ulmeanu M. (2018). Bases on external functional analysis tools the Task Book (TB) of the hybrid platform is constructed. (LAB 1, 2)

Estimated results: R1. Needs analysis report, which contains a process flow describing all used assessment tools and specific outcomes. R2. Curriculum Route Builder software application; R3. Requirements and specifications for the functional hybrid e-learning platform architecture.

Key success indicators: No. of sample group participants: 100; No. of initial CRB input variables: 6; Set no. of extended input variables: 1; Set no. of cognitive learning objectives: 3; Set no. of behavioural learning objectives: 3; Set no. of learning outcomes: 3; No. CRB flowcharts: 1; No. of designed software stand-alone applications: 1; Set no. of requirements and specifications: 1.

Deliverables: D1. Report on interpreted questionnaires used in needs analysis; D2. Report on interpreted interview data sheets; D3. Focus groups evaluation report; D4. Descriptive report on definition protocol for learning objectives and learning outcomes. D5. CRB programming protocol report; D6. Curriculum Route Builder software application; D7. Task book for hybrid e-learning platform.

WP2: Architecture and detailed design of hybrid e-learning platform

The second Work Package (WP2) has four main activities (A2.1 – A2.4) and is planned to be implemented during a period of twelve months (M8 – M19). Hereafter, the detailed activities, estimated results, key success indicators and deliverables are described in detail.

A2.1. (M8-M19): The hybrid e-learning interactive educational platform must be able to generate and deliver a student-centered customized curriculum for complex project development in engineering-based applications. The general architecture is based on the Task Book, ensuring that specific RS are reached within specified limits. Targeted software solutions integrated into the general architecture are: LabView, CSS, PHP, Talentlms. The advantages of each software solution, embedded with the developed CRB, allow metadata collection usage for generative personalized curriculum in a mass specified setting. (LAB 2)/ A2.2. (M8-M16): Design of content curriculum modules involves the compliance with several previously obtained results: extended input variables; cognitive learning objectives; behavioral learning objectives; learning outcomes; CRB and hybrid platform system parameters. A labor extensive activity, it involves the creation of a meta database with existing freeware curriculum content in the three main proposed systems (mechanical, software, electronical). Content curriculum is adapted and personalized for UPB available infrastructure. (LAB 1)/ A2.3. (M9-M16): A Pilot course is developed for testing of the main functional features of the platform. Course content must meet the same restrictions as stated in A2.2.

Testing of the course is undertaken on a randomly selected sample of 25 students (years 1 to 4) studying in industrial engineering area. Using SPSS an inferential statistics paired-samples t-Test is undertaken, to allow generalization of the results, beyond the gathered data. The paired-samples t-Test was selected for analysis, offering more statistical power, as it reduces possible variability between learners. This type of statistical test also coincides with the used assessment methods at UPB. 3-point analysis is preferred. The beginning of this activity was set in M9 (February 2021), as to coincide with the beginning of the academic semester at UPB, allowing the testing and implementation of the pilot course. (LAB 1, LAB 3)/ A2.4. (M15-M19): Result of the t-Tests are processed using SPSS and a report is developed by the team members. Significance of the results is determined by the p value of the analyzed data. A targeted value of $p \leq 0.05$ is desired. The tests evaluate the degree to which students fulfil the proposed learning objectives, through their obtained learning outcomes. The amount of difference between the two at three independent moments (3-point t-test), indicate the areas of the pilot test that need improving. Solutions for improvement are based on the previously developed RS. (LAB 1)

Estimated results: R4. Functional Architecture of Alfa version for a for hybrid e-learning platform; R5. Curriculum modules for complex project design in industrial engineering applications; R6. Pilot course for hybrid e-learning; *Key success indicators:* No. protocols: 1; No of architecture flowcharts: 1; No. of curriculum modules: min. 10; No. of pilot courses: 1; No. statistical tests used and interpreted: 1; *Deliverables:* D8. Functional protocol for architecture design of a hybrid e-learning platform; D9. Extensive report on curriculum content development; D10. Pilot course design report. D11. Report on testing procedure, implementation and result interpretation of pilot course.

WP3: Implementation and method demonstration

The third Work Package (WP3) has two main activities (A3.1 – A3.2) and is planned to be implemented during a period of five months (M20 – M24). Hereafter, the detailed activities, estimated results, key success indicators and deliverables are described in detail.

A3.1. (M20-M124): This activity involves the integration of the full curricula modules (developed in A2.2) in the hybrid e-learning platform environment. (LAB 1, LAB 2)/ A3.2. (M22-M124): Using DOE, a base experimental plan is developed at this stage, considering at least two independent natural variables. Functionality and repeatability tests are undertaken using focus groups. Results are statistically analyzed using Design-Expert V11 Software for multivariable regression analysis. A natural logarithmic transformation is preferred for simulation runs. Response surfaces are constructed for normalized variables in 3 dimensions: Ox – mechanical system, software system, electronical system; Oy - learning style, instructional strategy, delivery method, assessment method, competency level, complexity level and personal preferences; Oz – normalized intensity levels. Results are fed through a feedback loop into the architecture design of hybrid e-learning platform. The final concept of the platform is proposed for usage within the Faculty of Industrial Engineering and Robotics, offering a three-level customization designed for semester, year and final diploma complex project development. (LAB 1, LAB 3)

Estimated results: R7. Beta version for a hybrid e-learning platform; R8. Final hybrid e-learning platform for complex project development in industrial engineering applications.

Key success indicators: no. of experimental plans: 1; no. of focus groups: min. 3; no. of surface maps: min 15; no. of hybrid platform versions: 2.

Deliverables: D12. Report on Beta version design and implementation for a for hybrid e-learning platform; D13. Experimental plan with multivariable regression analysis; D13. Surface maps of individual learner evolution.

WP4: Project management and result dissemination

The final Work Package (WP4) deals with project management and result dissemination and has three main activities (A4.1 – A4.3). It is planned to be implemented during the entire period of the project (M1 – M24). All activities, estimated results, key success indicators and deliverables are described in detail below.

A4.1.(M1-M24). Project management is done throughout the entire duration of the project, so that each activity proposed in the project is provided with all the human, material and financial resources necessary to accomplish its

waging effectively and on time. A project management strategy is planned to be developed in the first month, so that all problems are detected early and effective solutions are found for any technical or financial barrier that may occur during the project implementation. Management involves: compliance with quality management strategy, establish policies for conflict solving, on-going assessment of activities, monitoring and reporting. (LAB 1)/ A4.2. (M3-M24). Publication in ISI quoted journals and conference proceedings are aimed in order to disseminate the original results of the project (LAB 1)/ A4.3. (M4-M7, M11-M13, M16-M18, M22-M24) Participation to scientific events (conferences, symposiums, webinars, seminars, workshops, etc.) and study visits are undertaken for both result dissemination and good practice . (LAB 1)/

Estimated results: R9. Management research strategy; R10. Published scientific papers and participations in international conferences

Key success indicators: No. of ISI published journal papers: 1; No. of published ISI conference papers: 3; No. of conference participations: 2; No. of study visits: 2.

Deliverables: D14. Intermediary Scientific Research Report. D15. Final Scientific Research Report.

Risk Management and Ethics

The fulfilment of the proposed objectives and the generation of the expected results depends to a large extent on the appropriate and rigorous risk management. For each identified risk, a response strategy is developed in accordance with SR ISO 31000: 2010 and SREN 31010: 2010. The qualitative analysis of the most prevalent technological, commercial, human resources and research risks are presented in Table 2, as well as the main contingency plans. Considering the total risk score of the project (1.82, compared to the maximum value 4) obtained from the qualitative risk analysis, it is concluded that the risk incidence rate is fairly low, and the project is feasible (Table 2).

Table 2: Qualitative analysis of the technological, commercial, HR and research risks for project implementation

Technological risks (TR) / (CP) Contingency plans - (SO1-SO4)	I*	W**	Score
TR 1. Inability to provide 100 eligible participants to the sample group within the specified timeframe. CP 1. A status evaluation of the participants' no. will be undertaken every week during A1.1. The planning is: M1-20, M2-50, M3-30. If the reports show inaccuracies in following the plan, participants will be selected from other Universities in Bucharest and Ilfov (same recruitment procedure), within the industrial engineering domain.	3	20%	0,60
TR 2. Sporadic unavailability of main e-learning environment. CP 2. A back-up of all e-learning content will be made on the freely available Moodle platform of UPB.	3	15%	0,45
TR 3. Incompatibility between the programming environments for generative design algorithms. CP 3. The main programming environment will be LabView; For compatibility with all online systems and embedded functions the Stand-Alone Toolkit will be used; As extra precautions CSS, C++ instruments will be used.	1	10%	0,10
Commercial risks (CR) / Contingency plans (CP) - (SO5, SO6, SO10, SO11)			
CR 1. Inability to make acquisitions for laboratory consumables and software licence in time for scheduled activities. CP 4. A necessary list will be put together and a university financed material stock will be made available.	2	5%	0,10
CP 2. SPSS software licence expiration. CP 5. The software licence is annually paid by UPB, and between the beginning of the calendar year and the approval of the acquisition budget, there can be gaps in payments. An IBM SPSS software discounts for students & faculty pricing plan is considered as a transition option.	1	13%	0,13
Human resources risks (HRR) / Contingency plans (CP) - (SO7)			
HRR 1. Withdrawal from project of a member. CP 6. At any time, implemented activities will be accompanied by descriptive deliverables, in the extent to which at least one other team member can substitute until a new one is employed.	1	15%	0,15
Research risks (RR) / Contingency plans (CP) - (SO8, SO11)			
RR 1. Proposed t-type models are not significant. CP 7. A feedback loop is designed within the sample group testing.	2	9%	0,18
RR 2. Proposed MRA models are not significant. CP 8. A feedback loop is designed within the focus group testing. Repeatability tests are provided.	1	11%	0,11
TOTAL SCORE		100%	1,82

*I - Importance: High-3; Medium-2; Low-1; ** W - Weight (%)

Scientific research, technological development and innovation activities within the project are subject to: Law no. 206/2004 on good conduct in scientific research and its subsequent amendments; Law 64/1991 on patents, republished, as subsequently amended, of Law 129/1992 regarding the protection of industrial designs, republished in 2007; and Law 8/ 1996 on Copyright and Related Rights. Compliance with specific EU legislation is ensured. Because the project involves collecting, processing and analyzing of personal data from human subjects, national GDPR Law no. 190/2018 and EU GDPR Regulation no. 679/2016 are complied with.

Resources and budget

The project is set to be implemented at the premises of UPB, using the appropriate infrastructure presented in Table 3. Each of the presented laboratories is destined for specific systems of the complex project development. Each activity detailed above has associated one of the three laboratories.

Table 3: Available infrastructure for project implementation and correlated estimated results

Laboratory & infrastructure	Estimated results
<p>LAB 1 (https://erris.gov.ro/TCM---UPB): 3D printing Equipment (50 3D printers), as follows: 5 Zortrax Inkspire 3D printers which are based on a version of the Stereolithography technology; one Ultrasound cleaning unit; 3 Zortrax Dual 3D printers using Material Extrusion (MEX); 5 Zortrax M300+ 3D printers (MEX); 3 Zortrax M300 3D printers (MEX); 2 BCN SigmaX dual extruder 3D printers (MEX); 10 3D Kreator 3D printers (MEX); 20 Crealty CR20-Pro 3D printers using (MEX); one Zcorp 310 3D printer using Binder Jetting technology; one Powder recycling unit for the ZCorp 310 equipment; one Projet 1500 3D printer using Digital Light Processing; Go!SCAN 3D Portable Scanner Creaform 3D; 25 web cameras; 100 desktop computers;</p> <p>Software: SolidWorks, Inventor, Catia, Cura, Simplify 3D, Meshmixer, Zprint Software; ProJet Client Software; Magics 13.0; VX Elements 2.0 SR3; Mimics Research 17.0, 3-Matic Research 11.0</p> <p>Robotics: 16 Arduino based toolkits each with Arduino Projects Book, Arduino UNO, and Breadboard-400 Pins.</p> <p>Target Complex Project Development Systems: MECHANICAL & ELECTRICAL</p>	R1, R3, R5, R6, R7, R8
<p>LAB 2 (https://erris.gov.ro/CTANM---UPB): Laboratory gear, Modelling & Simulation Software, General usage Software, Data acquisition software, Data acquisition and control systems, LabVIEW modules and toolkits: 1. Programmable power supplies; TrueRMS Multimeters; Soldering stations; Drilling machine; 3 axis CNC milling machine - GoCNC A3 Evolution. 2. Inventor, Solid Works, FlexSim, INCONTROL Enterprise Dynamics, ProPlanner. 3. Primavera P6, Adobe Photoshop, Microsoft Visual Studio, Microsoft Expression Studio 4 Ultimate, Microsoft Robotics Developer Studio R3/ LabVIEW 2011 Full Development System/ NI data acquisition equipment on USB, ISA, PCI, PCMCIA, Simulation Interface, NI SoftMotion, Robotics Module.</p> <p>Target Complex Project Development Systems: SOFTWARE & ELECTRICAL</p>	R2, R3, R4, R7
<p>LAB 3 (https://erris.gov.ro/CCMA---UPB): Mechanical simulation equipment: Testing system INSTRON 8800 100 kN; Testing system WALTER-BAI LVF 50 kN; dynamic extensometer SANDNER EX A 25-5X; axial extensometer EPSILON 3542-010M-100-ST extensometer 3541-010M-100-ST for testing fracture mechanics; Testing system Z010 ZWICK / ROELL 10 kN.</p> <p>Target Complex Project Development Systems: MECHANICAL</p>	R6, R8

According to the project detailed budget breakdown structure Table 4, acquisitions are planned for software licenses and consumables. Mechanical and electronic module insertion kits must be purchased for pilot testing and repeatability tests. The insertion kits are comprised of: Arduino CTC 101 Program – Full (10000 lei); Elergoo Sensor module kits compatible with Arduino (7000 lei); POXL Smart Robots for UNO programming (8000 lei) ZYLtech HyperCube Full DIY Kit - 300mm Cubic Build Volume w/ Dual Z (with Heated Bed Upgrade Premium high power 12V heated bed Frame color Aluminum Anodized) (22000lei).

Table 4: Detailed Budget Breakdown (in lei)

Budget chapter (expenses) - LEI	2020 (7 months)					2021 (12 months)					2022 (4 months)					Total 2020-2022
	Lei/hour*	h/ M**	Full time %	months/ member	Total 2020	Lei/hour	h/ M**	Full time %	months/ member	Total 2021	Lei/hour*	h/ M**	Full time %	months/ member	Total 2022	
1. Personnel expenses																
Project coordinator	250	20	25	1.75	8750	250	20	25	3	15000	250	20	25	1.25	6250	30000
CS I	250	20	25	1.75	8750	250	20	25	3	15000	250	20	25	1.25	6250	30000
PhD student	160	20	25	1.75	5600	160	20	25	3	9600	160	20	25	1.25	4000	19200
PhD student	160	20	25	1.75	5600	160	20	25	3	9600	160	20	25	1.25	4000	19200
Engineer	100	20	25	1.75	3500	100	20	25	3	6000	100	20	25	1.25	2500	12000
Engineer	100	20	25	1.75	3500	100	20	25	3	6000	100	20	25	1.25	2500	12000
Master student	100	20	25	1.75	3500	100	20	25	3	6000	100	20	25	1.25	2500	12000
Total Personnel expenses					39200					67200					28000	134400
2. Logistics expenses																
Software TalentLMS					30000											
Lucidchart solution					15000											
Module insertion kits					47000											
Laboratory Consumables					18000					35500					10000	63500
Materials					10000					17000					10000	37000

Dissemination, docum. etc.					4500					7300				2500	14300
Access to third parties infrast.					7830					11200				2600	21630
Total Logistics expenses					132330					71000				25100	228430
3. Travel expenses															
National and international scientific events, research and docum. internships etc.	5000	1			5000	5000	2			10000	5000	1		5000	20000
4. Indirect expenses															
Overhead					25906					29640				11620	67166
TOTAL BUDGET					202436					177840				69720	449996

* Gross salary including employer's taxes; ** h/M – hours / months.

Conclusion

The current research presents a detailed management planning procedure for the design and development of an e-learning interactive educational platform aimed at delivering a student-centered customized curriculum for complex project development in industrial engineering-based applications. Authors conducted a thorough literature research, identifying the main gaps, and tailoring the project structure so as, through the planned work packages, to fill in those gaps. A project plan with four work packages was designed, ready to be implemented in a 24-month time frame. The project was proposed to start together with the UPB academic year, so as to facilitate the testing of the pilot e-platform. Main resources were considered to be available within UPB's laboratories, with all the infrastructure described in the Erris platform. A Detailed Budget Breakdown was put together in order to identify the necessary financial efforts needed to implement the proposal.

Future research involves the improvement of the management planning procedure and project call application for funding of the proposal. The importance of the current research is even greater in the current socio-economic developments generated by the SARS-Cov2 outbreak.

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